

A Brief Overview of the Finding: The General Theory of Relativity Predicts Blackhole Formation

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Abstract

Black holes were anticipated by Albert Einstein's general theory of relativity, which he first suggested in 1915. It was predicted that there are areas of space where gravity is so intense that nothing can escape, not even light. Many observational and theoretical studies over the last century have offered convincing evidence for black hole existence. This overview summarizes the current understanding of black hole formation and the evidence supporting this prediction of general relativity. The study of black holes continues to be an active area of research, with important implications for our understanding of the universe and the laws of physics. In this article, We claim that the general theory of relativity made a solid prediction with regard to Sir Roger Penrose's discovery of black holes. In this article, we've examined the first post-Einsteinian result in general relativity the singularity theorem where Penrose first proposed the crucial idea of a closed trapped surface.

Keywords: Black holes, General theory of relativity, Singularity theorem

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1 Introduction

One of the most significant scientific theories of the modern age is the General Theory of Relativity, suggested by Sir Albert Einstein in 1916[1]. It revolutionized our understanding of space-time, gravity, and has been extensively tested and confirmed through various experiments. The prospect of black holes, which are immensely huge objects and so dense that nothing, even no amount of light can escape their gravitational pull, is one of the most intriguing predictions of the theory. Black holes were always thought to be completely theoretical ideas, but in recent years, astronomers have discovered a number of objects in the cosmos that seems to be black holes. Scientists have used computer simulations to explore how black holes are formed and evolved [2]. These simulations have demonstrated that the emergence of black holes is a reliable general relativity prediction that takes place in a variety of circumstances.

We aim to examine the proof for the development of black holes as predicted by the General Theory of Relativity in this essay. We have analysed the evidence for black holes in the universe and talk about their essential characteristics, such as their singularity and event horizon. We also consider some of the implications of black hole formation for our understanding of the universe as a whole, including the possibility of time travel and the nature of the universe's ultimate fate. Roger Penrose released a research paper on "GRAVITATIONAL COLLAPSE AND SPACE- TIME SINGULARITIES" on January 18, 1965, while he was still a student at Birkbeck College in London, England [3]. In that paper, Penrose used the notion of a Cauchy hypersurface to describe singularities, but more significantly, he also put out a completely original notion termed as closed trapped surfaces.

1.1 Method Of Discovery

The first and most intriguing question that comes to any researcher's mind is how he discovered the existence of black hole. We first need to grasp the theory underlying the evolution of the singularity theorem for a better comprehension of the finding which initiated in 1955 and lasts till 1965.

In this line of work the most significant work was done by Amal Kumar Raychadhuri when he submitted a paper in 1955 that contained the first singularity theorem ever and introduced the famous equation that would later named after him [3]. This was shortly after the father of relativity, Albert Einstein, passed away on April 18. Raychaudhuri was examining the possible paths that a bundle of light rays could take across the curved regions of spacetime in the 1950s. The area theorem's most crucial input, as stated by Raychaudhuri, was an equation that was used to represent this dynamic.

The famous Raychadhuri equation, which was derived from the Ricci identity, is as given below,

$$(\nabla_{\mu}\nabla_{\nu} - \nabla_{\nu}\nabla_{\mu})u^{\alpha} = R_{\rho\mu\nu}^{\alpha}u^{\rho} \quad (1)$$

by contracting α with μ the equation is simplified and given as,

$$u^\nu \nabla_\mu \nabla_\nu u^\mu - u^\nu \nabla_\nu \nabla_\mu u^\mu = R_{\rho\nu} u^\rho u^\nu \quad (2)$$

Rearranging the above equation the final equation obtained is,

$$u^\nu \nabla_\nu \nabla_\mu u^\mu + \nabla_\mu u_\nu \nabla^\nu u^\mu - \nabla^\mu (u^\nu \nabla_\nu u^\mu) + R_{\rho\nu} u^\rho u^\nu = 0 \quad (3)$$

1.2 The Raychaudhuri and Komar Singularity Theorems

The singularity theorem for irrotational dust is the primary finding that was published by Raychaudhuri in 1955 [3]. The same concepts were presented in Komar's article in the guise of an energy condition on $T_{\mu\nu}$. Considering the case where matter flows along the geodesic and hypersurface orthogonal time vector field u^μ a matter singularity can be obtained.

Assume $\Lambda = 0$ and perfect-fluid energy momentum tensor as

$$T_{\mu\nu} = \rho u_\mu u_\nu + p(g_{\mu\nu} + u_\mu u_\nu), \quad u^\mu u_\mu = -1 \quad (4)$$

whose velocity vector field u^μ is geodesic and irrotational. The energy density Q of the fluid diverges in the finite past along each integral curve of the expansion u^μ if it is positive at a given moment and holds.

1.3 Penrose Singularity Theorem

Sir Roger Penrose sought to study the Einstein equations in contrast to the Schwarzschild[3] but without adhering to the same spherical geometry presumption. He did this by combining a revolutionary idea called trapped surfaces with a branch of advanced geometry called topology. He contributed to the development of the Raychaudhuri-Landau equation. All the particles will eventually come together to form a singularity if they are all at rest with regard to one another. Gravity is a powerful force of attraction, hence this is accurate. When particles are sufficiently close to one another, many forces are at work to prevent a singularity from forming (one of these is "like charges repel"). Roger Penrose demonstrated that a singularity must form if light is unable to escape from a region, at which point the path of light will lead to the singularity. The event horizon of a black hole is this trapped surface. When the core of a huge enough star collapses at the end of its life, the gravity at its core is so intense that no other force can stop it from imploding into a small, ultra-dense zone, bending space-time indefinitely at its centre, and trapping light within its event horizon. Penrose established that some stars will unavoidably merge into a singularity that is encircled by an event horizon to create a black hole. If the space-time contains a non-compact Cauchy hypersurface Σ and if the convergence requirement is satisfied, there are future incomplete null geodesics for a closed future-trapped surface [1].

A Cauchy hypersurface is a moment in time that offers optimal initial value conditions for all the space. More specifically, it is an achronal hypersurface

that all causal infinite curves only need to meet once. If there is a Cauchy hypersurface Σ , then the space-time as a manifold is a product, $\mathbf{R} \times \Sigma$ all slices $\{t\} \times \Sigma$ being diffeomorphic Cauchy hypersurfaces. Another research by Penrose revealed that General Relativity's plane waves do not permit Cauchy hypersurfaces. The question of whether or not globally hyperbolic spacetimes are consistent with physical realism is connected to the so-called strong cosmic censorship conjecture. In order to demonstrate that the border of the future of the closed trapped surface is compact, the method of the sketched argument offered by Penrose [6] was to assume that null geodesics were complete. To accomplish that, one uses the concentrating of null geodesics that emerge orthogonally from the surface as shown in Yet, this boundary is essentially a boundaryless embedded submanifold.

1.4 Singularity

In a Lorentzian manifold, a singularity is an imperfect unending curve [7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13]. Though the curves only attain finite values of their canonical parameter, they cannot be continued regularly inside space-time. Hence, singularity theorems only establish the existence of geodesic incompleteness, which is by definition a necessary condition for singular spacetimes. As far as we are aware, there is no accepted singularity theorem that proves the existence of a geodesically complete singular space-time of this kind.

1.5 Reason for its Importance

In general relativity and mathematical physics, the singularity theorem is frequently cited as one of the most important theoretical discoveries [5, 7]. These theorems in particular produced numerous revolutionary new breakthroughs in theoretical relativity as well as intriguing results pertaining to the creation of the cosmos and the collapse of big stars. These findings point to a major gap in classical general relativity, posing a significant obstacle for the search for novel physics. Even though the precise makeup of the physics close to the gravitational singularity is yet unknown, it is commonly anticipated that quantum gravitational effects will give us a solution.

2 Conclusion

The development of black holes is in fact predicted by the general theory of relativity, according to the analysis of the scientific data. Many observations and experiments, such as the finding of gravitational waves caused by the collision of two black holes, have confirmed this prediction.

The idea states that anything, not even light, can escape the gravitational pull of a huge object as it collapses in on itself. As a result, the event horizon, an area of spacetime beyond which no information can be received or transmitted, is created.

Our knowledge of the universe has greatly benefited from the study of black holes, notably in the fields of astrophysics and cosmology. It has sparked the investigation of novel phenomena and the creation of fresh conceptualizations, such the Hawking radiation theory.

In conclusion, the discovery that the general theory of relativity predicts the emergence of black holes is an important development in modern physics that has advanced our comprehension of the cosmos. Sir Roger Penrose contribution in the field undoubtedly plays a crucial role of our understanding of black hole physics.

3 Declaration

The manuscript has been prepared through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript. All authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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